

Functional Split Evaluation in NTN for LEO Satellites

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Abstract

Functional split over non-terrestrial networks (NTN) is one of the key-enabling technologies in the next 5G+ and 6G networks, which allows the implementation of virtualized radio access network (vRAN), and the recent open RAN (ORAN) in NTN. Functional split is based on splitting the RAN functionalities into a centralized unit (CU) and a distributed unit (DU), aiming at reducing the processing requirements at the DU located close to the antenna. Even though functional split has been standardized and evaluated for terrestrial networks, its applicability in NTN has not been discussed up to now. Functional split is expected to be part of 3GPP NTN Rel-19, where regenerative payload is expected to be introduced in a new working item at the time of writing this paper. This work evaluates the different split options in NTN for low earth orbit (LEO) satellites based on NTN key performance indicators (KPIs) and highlights the challenges that hinders the implementation of functional splits in NTN. A new architecture is proposed to facilitate the implementation of functional splits in NTN while gaining the desired advantages compared to a transparent payload or a full gNB onboard.

1. Introduction

Virtualization has been part of radio access network (RAN) over terrestrial networks (TN) since 4G networks, where in order to simplify the network architecture and increase the scalability of the network in a cost-efficient manner, cloud RAN (cRAN) was initially introduced by splitting the base station (BS) into two entities, the radio unit (RU) and the base band unit (BBU). In the new 5G RAN architecture, the functionalities of the 5G BBU are split into three functional blocks, namely the centralized unit (CU), the distributed unit (DU), and the remote unit (RU). 3GPP has only defined the first two functional entities, while defining several split options over the protocol stack [1]. The functionalities implemented on the DU and the CU depend on the implemented split option as depicted in Fig. 1. Despite the fact that different split options were defined by 3GPP, only split option 2 was standardized. F1 interface was standardized over the interface between the CU and the DU [3]. ORAN, on the other hand defined split option 7.2x, while ORAN fronthaul interface is defined between the DU and the RU [10].

Regenerative payload whether it is a full gNB onboard or a gNB-DU, was defined by 3GPP [4], and it is expected to be introduced in a new working item (WI) in Rel-19. The applicability of the different split options in NTN is still not clear yet considering the different characteristics of NTN compared to terrestrial networks (TN) for which the functional splits were initially defined. The mobility of LEO satellites and the time varying long propagation delay on the feeder link between the gNB-DU onboard the satellite and the gNB-CU on the ground pose many challenges on the applicability of CU/DU functional split in NTN. In this work, we are going to present the challenges facing implementing functional splits in NTN, where different KPIs were used to evaluate the performance of split options. A description of the different functional splits is not going to be provided in this work considering the large amount of literature discussing functional splits in TN.

First, we are going to present the CU/DU architecture in NTN as defined by 3GPP. Second, we are going to evaluate the different split options based on NTN KPIs. Then, a new CU/DU architecture is presented, which might be more applicable for NTN considering the large RTT in NTN and the high mobility of LEO satellites.

2. CU/DU Functional Split Architecture in NTN

The next-generation RAN (NG-RAN) logical architecture with CU/DU functional splits in NTN as mentioned in [4] is depicted in Fig. 2, where the DU is implemented onboard the satellite, and the CU is implemented on the ground. The satellite radio interface (SRI) is carried over the feeder-link between the satellite and the gateway, which is used to carry the logical interface between the gNB-DU onboard the satellite and the gNB-CU on the ground. Considering that 3GPP has defined F1 interface between the CU and the DU, while ORAN has defined ORAN fronthaul interface between the RU and the DU, we are going to use CU/DU interface terminology to refer to the interface between the CU and the DU which could be F1 or any other interface depending on the implemented split option. The NR_Uu interface terminates at both the UE and the gNB-CU, and is carried over the service link between the UE and the gNB-DU and the feeder link between the gNB-DU

and the gNB-CU. Compared to a full gNB onboard the satellite, CU/DU functional split is considered for NTN to reduce the complexity and the power consumption onboard the satellite, which is one of the limiting factors when it comes to NTN. The efficient resource utilization and energy consumption can be used to enhance the coverage in the downlink, which is one of the main topics discussed by 3GPP for NTN. Additionally, resource sharing is one of the main advantages of having a DU onboard the satellite compared to a full gNB, as the centralized resources of the gNB-CU on the ground can be shared between many gNB-DUs, which increases the system efficiency, and enhances the resources

utilization. Resource centralization is one of the key factors for multi-connectivity, which makes gNB-DU onboard a good candidate for future 6G networks. Additionally, and in order to reduce the signalling latency when having the gNB-CU on the ground, a new architecture is proposed, where the gNB-CU onboard the satellite acts as a controller controlling the gNB-DUs onboard the surrounding satellites in a swarm-like architecture.

FIGURE 1. Functional Split Options

FIGURE 2. NG-RAN with a Regenerative Satellite Based on gNB-DU

3. CU/DU Functional Split Evaluation

The high mobility of LEO satellite, and the large propagation delay are one of the distinct characteristics of LEO satellites, which should be taken into account when evaluating functional splits, as different split options have different timing and bitrate requirements on the feeder link, which could be a challenge in NTN. For example, the available bandwidth on the feeder-link might be scarce and differs depending on the use case and the application, which makes lower split options not suitable for NTN due to the large bitrate requirements on the feeder link (CU/DU interface). Additionally, the limited available power onboard the satellite is yet another factor, as an energy efficient regenerative payload is required due to the high operational costs of LEO satellites. Scalability on the other hand is another important KPI due to the high implementation and launch costs. In this section, different criteria are used to evaluate the different split options, where the characteristics of NTN are used as a baseline for evaluating the different split options and their applicability in NTN.

3.1. Complexity Onboard the Satellite

LEO satellites have a limited power budget, and complexity onboard the satellite is one of the most important KPIs when evaluating CU/DU splits, as different split options have different complexity requirements onboard the satellite. Functional splits with high processing requirements onboard the satellite are not suitable for NTN applications and use cases. Fig. 3 shows that the complexity onboard the satellite increases for higher split options, as more functionalities are implemented in the gNB-DU. Reducing the complexity onboard the satellite reduces the energy consumption onboard the satellite, which might help increasing the satellite transmission power, which could be used to support more beams at the same time and increase the coverage area of the satellite, or to increase the equivalent isotropically radiated power (EIRP) per beam and to subsequently enhance the link level coverage per beam. As a result, lower split options might be a better option for implementation in NTN, where fewer functionalities are implemented in the gNB-DU side.

FIGURE 3. Complexity of CU/DU Split Options

3.2. Bit Rate Requirements

Due to the bandwidth limitation on the feeder-link, the bitrate requirement on the CU/DU is an important KPI when evaluating the different split options in NTN. The bitrate requirement model is based on [5], [7], [8], and [9]. In order to calculate the bitrate requirements, the following assumptions were made. The sample rate is assumed to be 30.72 Msps, the subframe duration is 1 ms, the number of OFDM symbols per sub-frame is 14, sub-carrier spacing is 15 kHz, and the bandwidth is 100 MHz.

Split Option 8:

This split option has a constant very high bit rate, which scales with the number of antennas [5], which is not scalable for massive MIMO scenarios. The traffic, as depicted in Fig. 1, is raw IQ samples in time domain between the RF frontend in the gNB-DU and the IFFT in the gNB-CU. This split option might not be suitable for NTN due to the very high and constant bitrate on the CU/DU interface, as the interface will be utilized regardless of the actual user traffic.

Split Option 7.1

This split option has also a constant high bit rate as the resource element (RE) mapping functionality is in the gNB-CU. The traffic is high but less than split option 8, as the data transmitted over the CU/DU interface is subcarriers.

Split Option 7.2x (ORAN)

The traffic is still constant and relatively high, but less than the traffic in split option 7.1, and it scales with the number of MIMO layers instead of antenna ports due to the digital beamforming on the gNB-DU [5].

Split Option 7.2

Since the RE mapping and the beamforming are performed on the gNB-DU, the traffic transmitted on the CU/DU interface is variable and lower than split option 7.2x, as the RE mapping is responsible for detecting the unused sub-carriers [5]. The bitrate requirement depends on the number of symbols transmitted, the number of quantized bits per symbol and control information necessary for further physical (PHY) layer processing [5]. The control information between the gNB-DU and the gNB-CU carries information such as beamforming, RE mapping, synchronization, and scheduling. Additionally, the variable data rate obtained in this split option, and onwards, enables having multiplexing and packetization between the gNB-DU and the gNB-CU, which is important to achieve an efficient resource utilization and spectral efficiency on the feeder-link.

Split Option 7.3

Since the scrambling, layer mapping, and modulation are included in the gNB-DU, the bitrate on the CU/DU interface

is variable and lower than split option 7.2 particularly because the modulation is performed on the gNB-DU.

Split Option 6

The bitrate is lower than split option 7.3 as transport blocks are transmitted on the CU/DU interface between the medium access control (MAC) (gNB-CU) and the PHY (gNB-DU). As a result, the load on this interface depends on the NR_Uu interface. Due to the dependency between the PHY and the MAC layers, Split option 6 has the highest scheduling control overhead compared to other split options [5], which affects the actual traffic, and should be taken into account in scenarios where the bandwidth on the feeder link is limited. Split option 5 and 4 have the same bitrate requirement as split option 6.

Split option 3, split option 2, and split option 1 achieve almost the same performance, and have a lower bitrate requirement, which make them suitable for scenarios, where the available bandwidth on the feeder-link is scarce.

FIGURE 4. Bitrate Requirements for Different Split Options [5]

Fig. 4 depicts the bit rate requirement for UE DL and UL in TN as described in [5]. It can be seen that the bit rate is higher for low split options, where split options such as 8, 7.1, and 7.2x have a high constant bit rate requirement. High split options such as split option 2 achieves a better performance when it comes to the bit rate requirements.

3.3. Timing Requirements

The reliability in 5G NR can be ensured by MAC layer hybrid automatic repeat request (HARQ) re-transmission and radio link layer (RLC) layer ARQ re-transmission [11]. RLC ARQ has a high latency and is sufficient to compensate the long RTT

in NTN, while HARQ, on the other hand, has a low latency, and needs to be adjusted in NTN in order to avoid HARQ stalling, which might occur due to the long propagation time between the UE and the gNB-DU in case HARQ is implemented in the gNB-DU onboard the satellite, and between both the UE and the gNB-DU as well as between the gNB-DU and the gNB-CU in case HARQ is implemented in the gNB-CU on the ground.

In order to compensate for the long RTT in NTN, one straightforward approach is to increase the number of HARQ processes in order to achieve an efficient resource utilization and avoid HARQ stalling (stop and wait issue), where the minimum number of HARQ processes should satisfy the following [11]:

$$N_{\text{HARQ},\text{min}} \geq \frac{T_{\text{HARQ}}}{T_{\text{Slot}}}$$

Where T_{HARQ} is the time duration between the initial transmission of one transport block (TB) and the corresponding ACK/NACK complete decoding, and T_{Slot} is the time slot duration, which corresponds to 1ms for a sub-carrier spacing SCS = 15 kHz [11]. As shown in Fig. 5, T_{HARQ} is given as the following in case HARQ is implemented in the gNB-DU (Split options 5, 4, 3, 2, and 1):

$$T_{\text{HARQ}} = [RTT_{\text{DUUE}} + T_{\text{sf}} + T_{\text{UE}} + T_{\text{gNB}} + T_{\text{ACK}}]$$

And as shown in Fig. 6, and in case HARQ is implemented in the gNB-CU (split options 8, 7.1, 7.2x, 7.2, 7.3, and 6), T_{HARQ} is given by:

$$T_{\text{HARQ}} = [RTT_{\text{CUDU}} + RTT_{\text{DUUE}} + T_{\text{sf}} + T_{\text{UE}} + T_{\text{gNB}} + T_{\text{ACK}}]$$

Where:

RTT_{DUUE} is the RTT between the UE and the gNB-DU.

RTT_{CUDU} is the RTT between the gNB-DU and the gNB-CU.

T_{sf} is the duration of the sub-frame [11], which is equal to the slot duration 1ms.

T_{UE} is the processing time at the UE side.

T_{gNB} is the processing time at the gNB-DU or the gNB-CU depending on whether HARQ is implemented on the gNB-DU or gNB-CU.

T_{ACK} is the ACK/NACK transmission time.

FIGURE 5. HARQ Duration in Case HARQ is Located in gNB-DU

FIGURE 6. HARQ Duration in Case HARQ is Located in gNB-CU

RTT_{CUDU} and RTT_{DUUE} vary depending on the altitude of the LEO satellite and the elevation angle, and the number of HARQ processes should be increased in order to compensate this long propagation delay especially for split options 8 to 6. For example, a LEO satellite at an altitude 600km can have an RTT_{DUUE} between 4ms and 12ms depending on the elevation angle [12], which means that in case of split options 8 to 6, the overall RTT ($RTT_{CUDU} + RTT_{DUUE}$) can vary between 8ms and 24ms, which can be compensated by 32 HARQ processes. It is worth mentioning that 32 HARQ processes is the number

of HARQ processes standardized by 3GPP for NTN [11]. On the other hand, implementing higher split options such as 5 to 1 might be a better option for LEO satellites at an altitude of 1200km and for GEO satellites, where the RTT_{DUUE} can be between 41.75ms and 541.14 ms for LEO 1200km and GEO respectively. Subsequently, the number of required HARQ processes can be between 40 and 500 [12]. On the other hand, implementing lower split options such as 8 to 6 for LEO1200 and GEO satellites requires 80 and 1000 HARQ processes respectively.

3.4. Multi-connectivity Support

Multi-connectivity (MC) is one of the most important technologies in NTN, which is expected to be part of NTN 6G networks. Functional split has an impact on MC and determines which MC technologies can be used in NTN depending on which functionalities are implemented onboard the satellite. Three MC technologies are taken into account in evaluating the different split options, which are coordinated multi-point (CoMP), carrier aggregation (CA), and dual connectivity (DC). DC relies on splitting the traffic after the packet data convergence protocol (PDCP) layer, which makes all split options suitable for DC. This is depicted in Fig. 7 taking split option 2 as an example, where the gNB-CU has the PDCP layer in addition to the radio resource control (RRC) or service data adaptation protocol (SDAP) for both the user plane or the control plane respectively, while the gNB-DU has the PHY, MAC, and RLC layers.

FIGURE 7. Dual Connectivity Using Two gNB-DUs (Split Option 2)

On the other hand, the performance of both CoMP and CA relies on what functionalities are centralized in the gNB-CU, as the more the centralization, the better the performance of CoMP and CA. As for the CA, the centralization of the MAC layer is important for a better performance. As a result, split options 6 to 8 are suitable for CA. Fig. 8 depicts CA taking split option 6 as an example. However, a single satellite might be used to provide carrier aggregation of two carriers (different bands) to increase the data rate provided to the user. In this case, it is better to have the MAC layer centralized onboard the satellite. In this scenario, all split options where the MAC layer is implemented in the gNB-DU is suitable for CA. This is depicted in Fig. 9 taking split option 4 between the RLC and the MAC layer as an example. CoMP, on the other hand, requires a great centralization on the physical layer, which makes split option 8 the best option for CoMP.

The different MC technologies require a strict synchronization between the gNB-CU and the connected gNB-DUs, as well as

between the gNB-DUs. The mobility of the satellite as well as the time varying delay between the gNB-DU onboard the satellite and the gNB-CU on the ground might have an impact on maintaining this synchronization as the satellite moves, which might have an impact on multi-connectivity. This should be taken into account when evaluating the performance of split options and MC in NTN.

Figure 8. Carrier Aggregation Using Two gNB-DUs (Split Option 6)

FIGURE 9. Carrier Aggregation Using One gNB-DU Split Option 4)

3.5. CU/DU Interface

The CU/DU interface should have different planes to convey different types of information as depicted in Fig. 10. The data plane is used to transfer the actual data. The control plane is used to transfer control signalling, which is required between the gNB-DU and the gNB-CU. Synchronization plane is used to maintain the synchronization between the gNB-DU and the gNB-CU.

FIGURE 10. CU/DU Interface Planes

This interface has different requirements depending on the implemented split option, where the nature of the traffic might affect the flexibility (packetization and multiplexing) that can be achieved over the CU/DU interface. Split options such as 8, 7.1, and 7.2x, which have a high constant data rate, use protocols such as common public radio interface (CPRI) and enhanced CPRI (eCPRI), which are based on time division multiple access (TDMA-based) [13]. These protocols might not be suitable for NTN due to the time varying large propagation delay, which makes maintaining the synchronization a very complicated task.

3.6. Beamforming Support

Implementing both the beamforming and the precoding functionalities onboard the satellite enhances the performance, as the sounding reference signal (SRS) can be used directly onboard the satellite to estimate the precoding matrix. Implementing the precoding on the ground leads to an outdated precoding matrix, which might degrade the beamforming performance. On the other hand, having the precoding in the gNB-CU might be useful for coordinating the different beams from different satellites as multiple gNB-DUs can be connected to one gNB-CU on the ground. As a result, lower split options such as 8, 7.1, and 7.2 might be suitable in case of high-altitude LEO satellites where there is a need to do beamforming onboard the satellite without taking beam coordination between multiple satellites into account. Split options such as 7.3 to 1 might be more suitable for low altitude LEO satellites, where the outdated beamforming information can be tolerated in order to support beam coordination between different satellites for applications such as MC.

3.7. Maximum number of supported DUs by a CU

Scalability is an important KPI in NTN, and the network should be able to provide a large number of cost- and energy-efficient satellites to provide a ubiquitous coverage, with the possibility to scale the network by increasing the number of connected gNB-DUs in a cost-efficient manner. The number of supported DUs by the CU increases significantly for higher split options, which is a critical factor to be taken into account. This is due to the fact that lower split options have high bitrate requirements on the feeder-link, which affect the number of supported connected DUs.

4. DU and CU onboard the satellite

Having the gNB-CU on the ground while the gNB-DU onboard the satellite could be a challenge due to the long latency associated with NTN, which poses a challenge when it comes to maintaining the synchronization between the DU and the CU for applications such as multi-connectivity. Additionally, the mobility of the satellite (gNB-DU) creates a new kind of challenge, where the CU/DU interface needs to be terminated and established continuously as the satellite moves, which causes continuous service interruptions. A straightforward approach would be the implementation of gNB-DUs onboard multiple satellites connected to a gNB-CU onboard a centralized satellite. Subsequently, and as depicted in Fig. 11, a swarm of satellites including the gNB-DUs and the centralized gNB-CU move together as one entity. This implementation allows providing a ubiquitous coverage and supporting of services and applications where the NTN gateways are not available or temporarily not operational. Additionally, this might be a better approach than implementing a whole gNB onboard the satellite due to the high costs associated with satellite operations. This approach brings the advantage of having the inter satellite link (ISL) connecting the gNB-CUs. As a result, the traffic could be routed from the different connected gNB-DUs via the centralized gNB-CU to be routed over the ISL between the different gNB-CUs. This is depicted in Fig 11.

This architecture is beneficial in order to reduce the latency associated with many RRC-signalling procedures such as random access channel (RACH), as the RRC terminates at the gNB-CU no matter what split option is going to be implemented. As a result, the signaling overhead is reduced significantly over the feeder-link. Lower split options such as 7.2, 7.3, and 6 might be suitable for this architecture.

Conclusion

In this study, we presented an overview of the different split options and their applicability in NTN. Different KPIs were used to evaluate the performance of functional splits. Many split options could be candidates for NTN, where different split options could be applicable for certain use cases and scenarios. Low split options such as 8, 7.1, and 7.2x have a constant bit rate, which might not be applicable for NTN in case of a limited resources on the feeder-link. However, these split options might be an option in case of a limited resources onboard the satellite and available bandwidth on the feeder-link. Protocols such as CPRI and eCPRI, which are TDMA-based, were defined for lower split options such as 7.2x. The strict timing requirements of these protocols make them unsuitable for NTN due to the long propagation delay.

FIGURE 11. gNB-CU and gNB-DU Onboard the Satellite

However, lower split options could still be applicable in combination of other protocols, which are not time-based. Split options 7.2, 7.3, and 6 could play an important role in NTN as they achieve a trade-off between the complexity onboard the satellite and the bitrate requirements on the CU/DU interface over the feeder-link. Split option 2 on the other hand, is a big candidate for NTN as the F1 interface was already standardized for CU/DU interface. It is shown that the timing requirement of the different split options depends on whether HARQ is implemented in the gNB-DU or the gNB-CU, where functional splits could be implemented in LEO600 without increasing the number of HARQ processes. Additionally, MC is another important KPI in evaluating the applicability of the different split options. Split options such as 7.2, 7.3, and 6 might be suitable for all MC technologies such as CoMP, CA, and DC. Higher split options such as split option 2, on the other hand, is more suitable for DC but not CoMP and CA. The synchronization required between the gNB-DU and the gNB-CU on one hand, and between the different gNB-DUs on the other hand, should be taken into account when evaluating the applicability of split options in NTN. Finally, a new architecture is proposed where the gNB-CU is implemented onboard the satellite as a centralized entity. This should facilitate the implementation of split options in NTN, as it helps overcoming the limitation associated with the long propagation delay as well as the mobility of the LEO satellites.

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